

A GALLERY OF UNUSUAL SPIRALS

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Introduction

The general intention of this review is to present graphically several interesting *transcendental spirals* based on related polar formulae. The idea is partially rooted in a previous work [1], especially when speaking of so called *hyperlog-spirals*. As a separate chapter will be presented here four brand new spiraling transcendental curves, e.g. *thurals*. In fact, each and every of these graphs is an inspiration by itself.

1. Esthetics of q -spirals

From the proposed generalization [1]

$$r = a e^{b\theta^q}, \quad q \in \mathbb{Q}$$

and based on different values of q parameter follows a palette of original spiraling curves under a possible term *hyperlog-spirals*. From now on, and for the sake of simplicity, let us call them shorter: *q -spirals*. Three the most fundamental such curves would be *logarithmic spiral*, *circle* and *hyperspiral*, or cases $q = 1$, $q = 0$ and $q = -1$, respectively.

It is quite possibly, even welcome, to analyze *q -spirals* both ways as one general geometrical entity or each separately but all that goes beyond the scope of this review. However, the choice of possible values for q here is mainly based on personal, esthetic reasons.

Finally, all the *q -spirals'* graphs are generated¹ using a natural simplification $a, b = 1$ and within different suitable but strictly allowed limits for θ .

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¹ By [Maxima](#) & [gnuplot](#)

Fig. 1.1: $q = 1/2, 0 < \theta \leq 4\pi$

Fig. 1.2: $q = -1/2, 0 < \theta \leq 4\pi$

Fig. 1.3: $q = 1/3, -4\pi \leq \theta \leq 4\pi$

Fig. 1.4: $q = -1/3, -4\pi \leq \theta \leq 4\pi$

Fig. 1.5: $q = 2/3$, $-4\pi \leq \theta \leq 4\pi$

Fig. 1.6: $q = -2/3$, $-4\pi \leq \theta \leq 4\pi$

Fig. 1.7: $q = 1/7$, $-4\pi \leq \theta \leq 100\pi$

2. Metaphysics of thurals

Four new, quite original transcendental curves (let us call them *thurals*) will be presented in this chapter. The very first one (Fig. 2.1) would be super-spiraling curve given with the polar formula

$$r = \theta^\theta \quad \text{or} \quad r = e^{\theta \ln \theta} ,$$

assuming $a, b = 1$. The second *thural* (Fig. 2.2) is formally analogous to the above and defined with the formula

$$r = \theta^{-\theta} .$$

The idea for its name comes naturally: *c-curve*. Finally, the last two spirals (Figs. 2.3 and 2.4) in this review would be defined with the formulae

$$r = \theta^{1/\theta} \quad \text{and} \quad r = \theta^{-1/\theta} .$$

Loop is what comes in one's mind when one takes a look at both curves, respectively.

Fig. 2.1: s-spiral, $0 < \theta \leq 4\pi$

Fig. 2.2: c-curve, $0 < \theta \leq 4\pi$

Fig. 2.3: super-loop, $0 < \theta \leq 6\pi$

Fig. 2.4: sub-loop, $0 < \theta \leq 6\pi$

Gratitude

To my mother Stoja, a fairy, with Love.

To my dear friend and great soul Nermin Jakirilić, cordially.

Acknowledgments

I would like to mention a permanent inspiration of the divine opus of Albrecht Dürer. We met about 532 years after. Part of that is spiritual enthusiasm of a dear friend Sava Kuzminac. Many thanks to Dr. Igor Sandalj, a real sport, for the book [2].

One long, fruitful discussion with Mr. Saša Doder was helpful in clarifying a role of the mathematical software as well as domains of the polar functions.

Last but not least, I would like to dedicate a few of these spirals to the mathematical class 1974-78, Banja Luka, as well as to dear professors Boško Čulibrk and Jelena Selec.

References

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